

two light treatments were in the main plots and the restorers in the subplots. Total dry matter (TDM) and yield were recorded at harvest.

Low light reduced mean TDM 47% and yield 57%. Reductions ranged between 25-71% for TDM and 38-78%

for yield (see table). TDM and yield were higher in IR54, IR58, IR134 19- 1 13- 1, and IR21916-128-2-2-3 under light. IR19058-107-1, Milyang 54, IR4422-480-2-3-3, and IR28178-70-2-3 all showed little reduction in TDM and yield percentages under low light. This

indicates their high yield capability under low-light stress.

Physiologically effective restorers, especially IR 19058-107-1, may be useful in developing superior rice hybrids for low-light monsoon areas. □

Physiological traits of certain restorers in hybrid rice breeding

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Restorers have been selected for cytoplasmic genetic male sterile lines based on fertility restoration and general combining ability for yield.

We tested the photosynthetic potential, growth, and yield efficiency of 20 purified IRRI restorers against controls Annapurna (early) and Jaya (medium) under field conditions during the 1989 wet season. We periodically drew samples to assess leaf area index (LAI) and dry matter (DM) production.

The photosynthetic rate (Pn) of the top three leaves at flowering was measured with the LI-6000 Portable Photosynthesis System at near saturated light (above 900 μ E/m² per s).

The high Pn entries IR58 and IR9761-19-1 had low LAI (see table), resulting in low canopy photosynthesis (Pn \times LAI). IR25912-63-2-2, with moderate Pn and

Physiological traits of selected restorers from IRRI. Cuttack, India, 1989 wet season.

Restorer	Pn (mg CO ₂ / dm ² per h)	LAI F	Pn \times LAI (g/m ² per h)	Total DM (g/m ²)			Yield (g/m ²)
				30 d	Flowering	Harvest	
IR36	36.3	2.48	8.9	99	619	887	339
IR46	28.9	3.78	10.9	86	617	901	262
IR50	34.3	2.46	8.4	88	394	537	207
IR54	30.4	3.80	11.5	109	691	789	289
IR58	40.4	2.05	8.3	121	420	569	234
IR64	35.5	2.88	10.2	123	600	758	256
Milyang 54	35.2	2.34	8.2	96	498	606	188
ARC11353	25.2	4.47	11.3	129	1124	1326	478
IR4422-480-2-3-3	26.2	4.15	11.1	140	886	1074	347
IR9761-19-1	39.3	2.28	9.0	105	550	714	198
IR13419-113-1	24.3	4.49	10.9	103	818	964	233
IR13524-21-2-3-3-2-2	35.5	2.60	9.2	118	534	707	228
IR19058-107-1	27.3	4.94	13.5	150	1213	1547	458
IR19392-211-1	33.3	2.47	8.2	130	564	751	238
IR21916-128-2-2-3	29.6	3.09	9.1	90	564	701	196
IR25912-63-2-2	35.3	6.39	22.5	110	1010	1365	456
IR27315-145-1-3	24.4	4.85	11.8	112	886	1161	389
IR28178-70-2-3	28.9	4.17	12.0	109	869	1192	482
IR29512-81-2-1	31.9	3.71	11.8	83	955	1227	476
IR29723-143-3-2-1	26.7	5.13	13.7	137	953	1194	490
Annapurna (check)	31.6	2.09	6.6	109	429	590	279
Jaya (check)	38.4	2.71	10.4	86	582	798	318
Mean	31.7	3.51	10.8	110	717	925	320
LSD(0.05)	3.4	0.95	3.5	ns	162	179	85

high LAI, recorded high canopy Pn, DM, and yield. IR19058-107-1 was especially efficient in LAI at flowering, DM production, and yield. To develop stable,

superior F₁ hybrids with high yield potential, IR25912-63-2-2 and IR19058-107-1 may be useful for heterotic combination of physiological traits. □

Yield potential

Effect of nitrogen level on the relation between sink-source parameters and grain yield

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We studied correlation coefficients between sink-source parameters and grain yield in lowland rice. In a field

experiment at IARI during the 1988 kharif (monsoon), seedlings of C-1907, Pusa 169, and Pusa 312 were transplanted at 20- \times 10-cm spacing.

The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications. Various growth and biochemical parameters were recorded at different stages and then correlated with grain yield. Nitrogen levels were in the main plots and cultivars in the subplots.

Grain yield correlated better with source than sink parameters particularly LAI and total chlorophyll content at flowering stage (Table 1). An increased

Table 1. Correlation values between different sink and source parameters and grain yield. IARI, 1988 kharif.

	<i>r</i> value ^a
<i>Sink components</i>	
Panicles (no./m ²)	0.46*
1000-grain weight (g)	0.49*
Spikelets (no./m ²)	0.46*
Sink size	0.42*
<i>Source components</i>	
LAI	0.70**
Total chlorophyll content at flowering stage	0.60**
Leaf N content at flowering stage	0.43*

^aSignificant at 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels.

Table 2. Effect of N level on LAI, unfilled grain percentage, and grain yield. IARI, 1988 kharif.

N level (kg/ha)	LAI	Unfilled spikelets (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
0	3.06	11.92	4.64
50	3.80	13.75	5.20
100	4.10	16.60	5.87
LSD (0.05)	0.67	2.08	0.39

LAI (source) due to applied N, however, led to a larger gap between grain number/m² and spikelet number/m². This resulted in a higher sterility percentage (Table 2). □

Rice varieties direct-seeded in puddled soil during boro season in West Bengal

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Boro season rice in West Bengal grows with supplemental irrigation during Nov-May after the wet season rice harvest in lowland and deepwater ecosystems. The area under boro rice has increased from 0.3 million ha in 1980 to 0.7 million ha in 1990. Average grain yield is 4.5 t/ha.

We direct-seeded 11 modern semidwarf rices in puddled soil at Chinsurah to decrease irrigation costs during boro 1985–86. Three methods were used: direct seeding of nonsprouted seed (NSD), direct seeding of sprouted seed (SD), and seedbed with sprouted seed and subsequent transplanting (SST). We sowed the nonsprouted seed 4 d before the sprouted seed.

Crop duration was slightly less under NSD (142 d) than under SD (146 d); plants in SST matured at 158 d (see table). Growth duration for HPU741, IR36, and IR60 differed more (26–27 d) than that for IET4786, IR56, and CR126-42-1 (12–14 d). Grain yield was approximately the same, but some varieties—IR36, IR50, CR126-42-1, and IET5851—yielded higher (5.2–5.6 t/ha) under NSD. IR56, IR60, and IET1444 yielded higher under SD, while IET4094 and IET4786 yielded higher under SST.

Results indicate that early harvest of direct seeded rice is possible without

Yield and growth duration of some rice varieties under 3 systems of crop establishment. Chinsurah, India, 1985–86 boro.

Variety	Duration ^a (d)				Grain yield (t/ha)			
	NSD	SD	SST	(NSD-SST)	NSD	SD	SST	Mean
Dular	120	123	132	12	2.0	2.2	2.9	2.4
CR126-42-1	144	144	158	14	5.2	4.3	4.3	4.6
IET1444	144	150	158	14	4.3	5.6	4.3	4.7
IET5851	142	144	158	16	5.2	4.5	4.6	4.7
HPU741	136	140	162	26	4.8	4.0	4.0	4.3
IR36	136	155	163	27	5.3	5.2	4.7	5.0
IR50	150	151	162	12	5.6	5.3	4.9	5.2
IR56	150	151	162	12	5.3	5.7	4.5	5.2
IR60	136	140	163	27	4.8	5.6	4.7	5.0
IET4786	151	156	163	12	4.7	5.4	5.6	5.2
IET4094	156	157	162	6	4.3	5.5	6.1	5.3
Mean	142	146	158	16	4.7	4.8	4.6	5.3

^aSeeding dates were 9 Dec, 13 Dec, and 13 Dec; transplanting date was 13 Jan.

sacrificing grain yield. Compared with transplanting, direct seeding shortens the growth duration an average of 16 d, and

saves four to five irrigations during the reproductive phase. □

Variation in rice husk-kernel ratio (HKR)

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Increasing the ratio of grain to biomass (harvest index [HI]) is a way to improve rice yields in the tropics. Reduced partitioning of dry weight to the husk could improve HI.

We examined seasonal variations in HKR in modern rice varieties BR1, BR3,

BR9, BR12, and BR16 grown at the BRRI farm during the 1985–86 transplanted aus, transplanted aman, and boro seasons. Plots had four 5.4-m rows each with 25- × 20-cm spacing and were laid out in randomized complete block design with five replications. Fertilizer was 80-26-33 kg NPK/ha, 23 kg Zn/ha, and 100 kg gypsum/ha.

Filled spikelets (specific gravity = 1.10) of each harvest were separated with salt solution and dried at 80 °C for 5 d.

Husk and kernel weights were determined for 100 g seed/season per

Table 1. Varietal difference in HKR in 3 seasons. BRRI, Gazipur, 1985-86.

Variety	HKR		
	Transplanted aus	Transplanted aman	Boro
BR1	0.256 ± 0.002	0.232 ± 0.004	0.229 ± 0.004
BR3	0.269 ± 0.003	0.261 ± 0.001	0.263 ± 0.004
BR9	0.290 ± 0.002	0.261 ± 0.003	0.260 ± 0.001
BR12	0.267 ± 0.003	0.253 ± 0.002	0.250 ± 0.003
BR16	0.267 ± 0.002	0.259 ± 0.002	0.258 ± 0.001
Av	0.270	0.253	0.252

Table 2. Genetic parameters for HKR in 3 seasons.^a BRRI, Gazipur, 1985–86.

Season	Range	Mean	Variance ratio ^b	PCV	GCV	ECV	Heritability (%)	Mean genetic advance (%)
Transplanted aus	0.250–0.298	0.270	36.53**	5.377	5.035	1.888	87.66	9.71
Transplanted aman	0.227–0.273	0.253	24.96**	5.280	4.803	2.194	82.74	9.00
Boro	0.222–0.276	0.252	31.21**	5.937	5.500	2.237	85.79	10.49

^aPCV = phenotypic coefficient of variability, GCV = genotypic coefficient of variability, ECV = environmental coefficient of variability. ^b** = significant at 1% level.